

Harmonious discourse markers: Understanding the social justice ideology discourse

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This article makes the claim that the social justice ideology that has become hegemonic and institutionalised throughout the universities of the Anglosphere is best understood by analysing what I call 'harmonious discourse markers'. Using discourse analysis, a methodology itself embedded in the social justice ideology, it is shown how the connotative value of language is manipulated to index a false compassion and harmony. The ideological code employs antonymous discourse markers such as 'safe/dangerous' and a family of 'values' such as 'diversity, equity and inclusion' to make the discourse seem unimpeachable. Throughout the discourse, it is the esoteric meanings of the ideological tokens that are prioritised over the exoteric meanings. The objective of the discourse is to polarise and demonise the alternative discourse on grounds of moral standards and discompassion. In doing so, its attempt to invert power structures is seen to be a charitable endeavour even if it directly discriminates against the ethnic majority. All ideologies are involved in the weaponization of language. The social justice ideology and its revolution of empathy is no different, but it is cleverly disguised as the discourse is wrapped in terms of compassion and inclusion.

Keywords: Discourse; Diversity; Esoteric Meanings; Exoteric Meanings; Ideology; Inclusion; Social Justice

"When I use a word," Humpty Dumpty said, in rather a scornful tone, "it means just what I choose it to mean—neither more nor less." (Through the Looking Glass/Lewis Carroll)

1. Introduction

Nietzsche (1992) believed that herd morality was one of the greatest inhibitors to cultural development, and would no doubt have considered the so-called 'woke' culture a manifestation of his 'slave morality'.¹ Arguably, we live in a time where herd morality combined with an oppressive groupthink has led to what Nietzsche might have called a new 'genealogy of morals'.² It could be argued that the basis for this moralist hegemony is something called 'social justice'. The schema of reasoning implied in social justice thinking has come to

the fore at a time when digital saturation has brought with it a culture of memes (what Dawkins calls 'idea viruses'), hashtags (targeted communication) and other forms of online pseudo-engagement such as 'phatic posts' which have surely contributed to the polarisation of our communities (McDonald, 2021; Radovanovic & Ragnedda, 2012).

The consensus is that over the last fifteen years or so this new moralism of sorts has emerged principally in western English-speaking countries. As one of the ideological foundations of this moralism, it is surprising that the notion of social justice has been ignored in the discourse analysis literature. That is until you appreciate that discourse analysis as a methodology is itself embedded in the post-modernism that the social justice ideologues perpetuate. Discourse analysts tend to share the same political orientation as indeed they themselves admit (Oliphant, 2015). Nonetheless, using their methodology this article makes the case for social justice to be understood as an ideology which aspires to create a new moral code. By understanding better some of the discursive tools used to impose and enforce this ideology, we can interpret how this new kind of practical postmodernism attempts to invert power structures. To do this, I will consult a dataset that comprises online material posted by universities in the English-speaking world for it is widely understood that it is in these institutions that the new moralism and its fervour are at their most pervasive.

2. Background

It could be claimed that in the English-speaking western world, the moral territory has been divided up and hypermorality has become the norm. Identity politics nowadays is characterised by a group of ideologues who try to reserve a monopoly on this hypermorality (Gehlen, 1967; Leonard, 2018). The task of the hypermoralist inquisitor is to turn every issue into a moral one; then any opponents to their incessant moralising and assimilationist thinking can be labelled 'immoral'. The notion of immorality is in fact key to understanding the totalising social justice ideology which attempts to racialise everything considered counter to the ideology. Social justice attempts to embrace as many iniquities as possible providing they pertain to some kind of minority status and align with the meta-narrative of marginalisation. The intention is to conflate struggles of certain interest groups with universalising judgements and claims.

The ultimate objective is to create a hyper-sensitised victim culture based on *one* set of beliefs. According to the ideology's meta-narrative, racial inequality must be due to racism and racism alone. What is more, this racism, homophobia, transphobia, Islamophobia etc.—all of which can be conflated into racism when the need requires—*must* be systemic and endemic.

The ideology dictates that every aspect of our culture must be riddled with racism—in essence this is the flawed basis of Critical Race Theory (CRT). This then is one of the axiomatic propositions of the ideology and to challenge it is in itself apparently ‘racist’. There must be an obfuscation of the plethora of economic, social and cultural factors all of which contribute to racial inequality. Social justice has been colonised by a form of closed thinking and this closed thinking has in turn contributed to the herd morality.

The herd employs a number of discursive tools to persuasively enforce its rhetoric. One of these tools is micro-aggressions which are no longer framed in terms of intent, but in terms of impact and anyone can claim to be ‘offended’.³ Micro-aggressions tend to be unintentional (Di Gennaro & Brewer, 2018), and the interpretation of the ‘offended’, the ‘micro-aggressed’ is always prioritised. In this new world of hyper-sensitivity, the power of language assumes an absolute centrality for words, phrases and idioms are tokens of potential racism. Much of language is in fact now no longer ideologically neutral and can instead be perceived to be ‘deviant’. The idea is to characterise anyone that questions the social justice ideology as ‘morally repugnant’. The use of the word ‘deviant’ is an ideological token—it is easy to invoke *doxa*, appeal to a unified opinion and apparently shared linguistic consciousness if opponents can be marked as *aberrant* in some way. As with most ideologies, the social justice ideology aims therefore to hegemonise patterns of social control through the manipulation of the connotative value of language, and in doing so reconfigure patterns of power and create new linguistic and social hierarchies which extend from the reiterative use of certain discourse markers.

In order to bring about this hegemony in the public domain, the social justice ideology hopes to polarise the alternative discourse and create a Schmitt (1932) like friend/enemy dichotomy. This polarising effect can be maximised through the use of what I call ‘harmonious discourse markers’. As we will see, the effect of these discourse markers is to render the social justice discourse unquestionable and beyond reproach because the discourse markers index compassion and ideological alignment with this worldview. The alternative discourse is by definition insidious, discompassionate and inherently ‘racist’. This reductionist line of thinking goes against the enlightened principles on which the institutions that now promote the social justice ideology most emphatically were founded. As we will see, there is also a degree of concept creep where the word ‘justice’ is concerned. An attempt has been made to render all topics that pertain to perceived marginalised group identities fitting the ideology into ‘justice’ related issues (e.g., climate, gender, sexuality, menstruation, information, etc.). Let us now take a closer look at how the social justice ideology works, but first one should say a word or two about the data set and methodology.

3. Method

3.1. Data set

The data set comprises the websites of 100 universities based in the US, the UK, Australia, New Zealand and Canada. This data set was chosen because the social justice ideology pertains overwhelmingly to the English-speaking world and in particular to English-speaking universities. Using *Excel*, a random sample was taken from 166 UK higher education institutions, 1749 US universities, 101 Canadian universities and 40 Australian universities as listed by *uniRank*. A random sample of 25 universities from each country was selected in order to ensure the countries were given equal weightings. Had a random sample been taken on the overall compiled list of English-speaking universities, then the chances are the entire list more or less would represent universities based in the US. Cluster random sampling was not used because of the risk of sampling errors and the unnecessary complexity involved.

Without exception, each and every website that made up the dataset devoted pages to social justice/DEI (diversity, equity and inclusion). In many cases, the wording is more or less copied and pasted from one university website to another. Universities prefer to simplify complexity to attract others rather than discuss trade-offs, options and positions with their stakeholders. It is recognised that one of the limitations of this research is that a website is a signal simplification platform. I am not suggesting that universities are themselves 'polarisation actors' (Kushawa et al, 2022). Nonetheless, this data set was examined to analyse what statements universities made about their 'social justice policy'. As we will come onto see, universities in the Anglosphere confer degrees in 'social justice' and there are large numbers of university departments/Institutes/centres devoted to social justice, inclusion, diversity, belonging, hate speech, etc.

3.2. Procedure

In this article, I use discourse analysis to explain how ideologies treat different epistemologies (taking epistemology as a kind of meta-knowledge) through the use of discursive tools. The discourse analysis approach is both interpretative and explanatory, and assumes that certain words and syntactic structures are used in a specific discourse in a conscious, non-coincidental way in order to produce and reproduce a desired power relation (Chouliaraki & Fairclough, 1999; Hodge & Kress, 1993; Van Dijk, 1993; Wodak, 1996). The analysis aims to reveal the discursive nature of the power relation that has been created and to show how the discourse operates ideologically. In doing this, it assumes that the relationship between discourse, the underlying culture and social structures is dialectical.

4. Results

Althusser (1971) reminds us that ideology works by disguising its true ideological nature. Social justice should be thought of as an ideology because it promotes the interests of a particular group while pretending to be in the interest of society as a whole. It seeks to create and propagate a secondary reality (Wodak, 1989) where certain group identities are unquestionably marginalised and where the host society (providing it is predominantly white) is *inherently* opposed in some way to these marginal groups.

Althusser and Wodak were of course talking about ideologies *per se*, and not social justice specifically. Even if it disguises its true ideological nature, aren't there other reasons to think of social justice as an ideology? Firstly, social justices are only social justices if judged so by the parameters of 'critical consciousness' but the word 'critical' has become an ideological token—here it simply means the consciousness of the social justice ideologue. As an example, according to the social justice theory the study of mathematics can only be legitimate once it is 'decolonised'. Secondly, the key dogma with the social justice ideology is 'the personal is the political'. For example, matters of sexuality once belonged in the private domain. Not anymore, these are now the fuel for political advocacy. One obvious linguistic manifestation of this is the public display of pronouns across all social media platforms. Never before has an ideology attempted to change something as fundamental as pronouns—the bits of grammar that refer to 'you' and 'I', but these are now markers of solidarity for those who wish to normalise trans and non-binary gender identities.

Social justice as the term is employed in Anglosphere universities at least is a useful misnomer.⁴ It is a misnomer because it has little to do with justice in the sense of civil rights and has nothing to do with any notion of distributive justice. The movement is not interested in poverty, starving populations in various parts of the world or even really the empowerment of women in the parts of the world where it is needed. The social justice ideology frames its statements in sanctimonious language but shows no interest in real disadvantaged groups such as white, working-class males in Britain (Baars et al., 2016). On the other side of the Atlantic, many of the poorest counties in the United States are to be found in Kentucky and are overwhelmingly white (between 90 and 100%) and have had a mean income well below the average black American for several decades (Tackie, 2021). By definition, these communities in the US and the UK *cannot* be subject to any social justice initiatives—with perhaps the ironic exception of 'white privilege'.

Instead of focusing on such real hardship and poverty, the movement is interested in the empowerment of women in places where equality was achieved long ago; it is interested in the promotion of gay rights in places

where there is even positive discrimination for the LGBTQ community and it is focused on the promotion of gender identities even if most non-binaries have little interest in instrumentalising their sexual proclivities. Were it not for the fact it is an ideology, the social justice ideology would aim to heal ethnic divisions as opposed to seeking division and in doing so making them exponentially worse. Social justice functions therefore first and foremost as propaganda, and the masses can only be won by propaganda. The new 'secondary reality' and its ideological framing in terms of compassion and justice appears to be unimpeachable but within it lie structures of hypocrisy and racism. Instead of seeking equality, it seeks racial hierarchies and wholesale discrimination of the majority be it ethnic or on the basis of gender, sex or sexuality.

By insisting on racialising everything, it pursues in the name of anti-racism its own racism. Social justice and its 'critical consciousness' claims to be tackling 'systemic power', but actually seeks solely to create its own systemic power. Student led campaigns to defund and/or abolish urban police departments in the US is a good example of attempts to invert power structures. With such campaigns, it should be obvious that social justice is an ideology for activists—it promotes agitation, disruption and protest and for this reason has flourished at the most 'liberal' universities. There is a nihilistic element to the implementation of these social justice measures too. Its architects tend to be the same elite that they are meant to be attacking—white, middle class, cis-gendered, able-bodied etc. to use the social justice terms. The elite has turned on itself and embraced 'white guilt'. Frankenberg (1993, p. 236) defines 'whiteness' as 'the production and reproduction of dominance rather than subordination, normativity rather than marginality, and privilege rather than disadvantage'. The social justice elite talk about 'experiencing whiteness' and the 'ideology of white superiority and hegemony', but seem to have little understanding that they are peddling their own radical and unjust ideology, one which claims that the ethnic majority are all racists.

Where discourse is concerned, the starting point should be that language users explicitly or unwittingly articulate their ideologies through language and communication. Thompson (1984) argues that ideology must be analysed by situating it in the social world and paying attention to the power of language. I do not use the word 'ideology' because I wish to suggest that the notion of 'social justice' is somehow false. I use it because as with all ideologies we are concerned with group interests (here, perceived 'marginalised' groups) that are defined by categories of identity and because there is, I believe, a manipulative force being expressed throughout the social justice discourse. There has been a great deal of research on the language of ideologies with much of the focus being on fascism, Nazism, neo-Nazism, communism etc. (Hodgkinson, 1955; Klemperer, 1946; Seidel, 1961; Sauer, 1978)—the purpose

of many of these studies has been to understand better how language is used to disguise the insidious nature of the beliefs that underpin the ideology. But what if an ideology is built on the narrative of emancipation and thus couches its creed and rhetoric in terms of 'progress', 'social justice', 'inclusion', 'diversity' and 'tolerance'? Surely, such a belief system embedded in the discourse of compassion could not have a more sinister objective? All ideologies are involved in the weaponisation of language (cf. Balosa, 2024; Chaka, 2024; Hannaford & Alexander, 2024; Huang, 2024; Kruger-Marais, 2024; Mapuya, 2024; Motaung, 2024; Ndlangamandla, 2024; Nkhi & Shange, 2024; Salmani Nodoushan, 2024; Xu & Fang, 2024). The social justice ideology is no different, but it is cleverly disguised as the discourse is expressed in terms of compassion and inclusion.

It is worth noting that whilst it is an ideology which seems Christian in appeal (with universities brandishing their 'mission statements'), its practitioners are largely urban atheists.⁵ Social justice, Critical Race Theory, and the like are not in any way some brand of Christianity even if attempts might be made to disguise them as such. Social justice is an ungodly ideology, an *ersatz* religion that ignores scriptural reasoning and that threatens its critics with cancel culture. Unlike a religion, all that matters with social justice ideology is that you signal and piously endorse in public (for political convenience) the 'virtues' of the ideology. It matters little if you or the institution actually really believe in these 'virtues'. Indeed, the non-absolutist 'progressives' can often be heard mocking them in private. The movement might appear eschatological in nature and it certainly has an evangelical drive, but it has little to do with Christian compassion.⁶ It is more of a mythology or secular gospel whose practitioners seek false gods.

The social justice code and its harmonious discourse markers ('diversity', 'inclusion', 'equity', 'progress' etc.) is repeated unthinkingly and the lexical reiteration adds in turn to the cohesive force of the ennobling rhetoric (Wodak, 1989). Ideological structures become codified through the systematic repetition of such language. Indeed, as with many effective ideologies, the rhetoric is so oratorically persuasive it is difficult to conceptualise a response that does not sound discompassionate and therein lies the objective. The code might be thought of as a type of Cassiresque 'word veneration' (Cassirer, 1946, p. 45) where it is believed the sermonic and repeated use of a word can somehow transform reality. Anyone who has spent any time on a university campus in the Anglosphere in recent years is already acutely aware of this code and in general the pervasive anti-Enlightenment agenda. Students are encouraged to see everything through the lens of race and gender. Social justice has become a vague cover term for a whole host of apparent injustices: during various social justice months/weeks/days at English-speaking universities, students are encouraged to embrace non-binary gender identities and to

identify as black to show solidarity with George Floyd. Ritualised denunciations of ‘whiteness’ are now common place on US campuses, and white students at a number of British universities are invited to apologise for their ‘white privilege’ even if few really understand what this means.⁷ Let us now take a closer look at the discourse markers of this ideology.

4.1. ‘Harmonious’ and antonymous discourse markers

In any kind of ideological framework, language is being constantly assigned new indexical meanings in order to associate language use with social power. Words that are key to the ideological code are typically endowed with new shades of meaning. Intersubjective ideologies may emerge from this reiterative language use in institutionalised social contexts. Below, we will look at a few examples of discourse markers central to the social justice ideology. The social justice discourse functions as a powerful source of indexical meanings—meanings that connect discourses and point to ideological identities. The discourse markers discussed below are all meant to index a sense of harmony and compassion (and their antonyms):

Table 1
Harmonious Discourse Markers

	Use of Antonymous Discourse Markers:	Indexicality	Effect	Objective
Harmonious Discourse Markers	Safe/dangerous Hope/hate	Ideological alignment	Delegitimisation of opponent Sense of ‘safe’ community	‘Engage’, ‘Empower’ and become a ‘champion’ (of social justice causes)
	Harmonious ‘Values’: Diversity } Equity } Social Justic Inclusion }	Compassion and harmony	Sense of ‘just’ community	

Generally speaking, there is a tendency for speakers to categorise experiences in terms of dichotomous contrast (Lyons, 1977). Antonymous discourse markers which convey meanings that are not primarily referential are useful ideological tools for they are particularly powerful as polarising mental

representations. Such discourse structures and clausal expressions serve two functions: firstly, they enact the underlying ideology and their second function is to act as a rhetorical means of persuasion (cf. Allan & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015). In order to enforce a polarising structure between 'us' and 'them', the social justice ideology tends to organise schematically general opinions and socio-cultural values about relevant social justice issues. Certain key binaries often employed in a performative and artificial style of communication function as ideological signals. They also act as shibboleths (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021b)—use of these expressions guarantees that you are communicating with someone who is either virtue-signalling or who has opted for dogma and rejected critical reasoning ('critical' in the non-ideologised sense). Their use is not only institutionalized in Anglosphere universities, but increasingly in the corporate world as well.

Lexical-semantic opposition is manipulated as a discursive tool to serve ideological purposes. Antonyms can be used in ideological discourse to maximise this difference between 'us' and 'them'. Out of all the sense relations (hyponymy, synonymy, meronymy), 'antonymy is probably the most readily apprehended by ordinary speakers' (Cruse, 1986, p. 97). It has been shown that children as young as three years old recognise antonyms. It seems that every word that is pronounced calls forth its opposite in the consciousness of the speaker and hearer.⁸ We think of 'the rich' and 'the poor' comes to mind as the maximal contrast. We don't tend to conjure up straight away images of people who are 'middle of the road'—images of this mass of people who are neither rich nor poor come to the mind less readily. 'Safe' and 'dangerous' is clearly such a strongly canonical oppositional pair. During the Covid 19 pandemic, there was much talk of safetyism. The ideological advantage of binary terms or antonymous pairs is that they permit nuance free language—right/wrong; victim/perpetrator; racist/anti-racist. Binary terms are used to help reify group membership (and division): you are either with us or you aren't. The safe/dangerous binary opposition permeates in fact almost all of social justice discourse. This is a false epistemological construct that has risen to the level of its own rather narcissistic ideology. It is false because the behaviour that is described using these adjectives has nothing to do with any sense of peril or lack of peril. It is simply a means of deligitimising en masse any opponent to the ideology by labelling them as some kind of 'threat'.

A space is 'safe' if anyone who might challenge the social justice ideology can be 'excluded'. A person or behaviour is 'dangerous' if they do not adhere to the tenets of the social justice ideology. A critically aware individual is thus 'dangerous' because they may for no explicit ideological reason undermine the social justice ideology. They are a threat to the cohesion of the group. It is a rhetorical means of deligitimising an opponent's views by associating him or her with peril, hazard and risk. The social justice ideology is wrapped in an

emotive rhetoric that encourages people to be oversensitive and easily offended—a ‘dangerous’ person could leave them ‘triggered’. It is hoped that in turn this will lead to acts of (fake) rage and that these acts of rage can be used as a justification for claims to power. Universities in the Anglosphere are full of this language. Here are a few examples (my italics):

Surveys indicate that LGBTQ students who do not feel *safe* are likely to skip class, or even days of classes, out of fear for personal *safety*. Students who can identify a supportive community member are more likely to feel a sense of *belonging* at their school than those who cannot. (University of Chicago)

Social Justice Education Workshops are described as: ‘a *safe* environment for people to start their exploration and reflection on social justice issues’. The highlights of the workshop include:

- Checking our biases
- LGBTQ friendly workspaces
- Allyship
- Fostering a culture of inclusion and belonging
- So you want to be an anti-racist?
- Microaggressions

(University of New Hampshire)

Sexual orientation and gender are protected characteristics and everyone has the right to feel *safe* and feel as though they *belong* without fear of discrimination based on who they are. We promote visual symbols like the LGBTQ+ banner and the red umbrella—which is the international symbol for sex workers. (University of Manchester)

Students across universities in America claim that ‘society will be *safer* without police’. In accordance with the ideology, this means society will be more harmonious if we can dismiss those who seem to be an affront to the social justice ideology because they are white. This statement is very obviously ideological and almost on a par with the Orwellian ‘WAR IS PEACE’. Providing we use the dictionary meaning of the word ‘safer’, we know that the statement is factually incorrect and cannot stand up to intellectual scrutiny. These developments are shocking for they are so far removed from empirical truth. In some cases, such as the University of California, they have institutional support.

The purpose with this kind of language (‘safe/dangerous’) is to create a moral panic. One tactic to create panic is of course through the use of the word ‘emergency’—talk of ‘climate emergency’ might be reasonable enough but the

activist group 'Human Rights Campaign (HRC)' declared a 'LGBTQ emergency' in America in June 2023. Here we can see the safe/dangerous ideological schema being reactivated at subsequent levels (Irvine & Gal, 2000). This was in response to certain States trying to prevent school drag performances for three-year-olds and gender surgery for minors. In light of the 'emergency', HRC 'advises against travel to Florida'. In using such language, it attempts to mirror and thus give the impression it has the status of that of a government department. In turn, this might make its emergency rhetoric appear more legitimate. Universities such as the University of California (Davis) offer 'emergency grants'—you can only apply if you 'identify as part of the LGBTQPIA+ community'. It is 'inclusive' to this 'marginalised' group but everyone else is excluded. A number of universities such as Rutgers run Centers for Social Justice with their own 'Trans Emergency Resources'.

Sanctimonious safetyism has become a powerful ideological tool and the undisputed dogma of public discourse in Anglosphere universities. To refute the propaganda is to embrace 'danger' and all that entails. It is to engage with some kind of 'deviancy' and this alleged deviancy is stigmatised typically through the use of labels such as 'racist'. These labels have been recycled to such a degree they have become semantically rather vacuous and thus counter-productive. The objective with this kind of labelling is to project and reproduce stigmata at other levels through the process of association. So, anyone who is associated with someone or some kind of organisation that uses 'dangerous' speech should in turn be stigmatised and 'cancelled'. The purpose is to isolate the 'offender' by creating networks of disassociation and thus normalise the social justice discourse. The ideologues—or 'influencers' in the digital herding literature (Kusahawa et al., 2022)—have created a taxonomy of fear and safetyism has become the prevailing orthodoxy. The institutions that were meant to be protecting free speech, such as academia, became the first to enforce the conformity, the first to dispense with any notion of critical thinking. Indeed, critical thinking has been replaced by 'critical consciousness'.

'Hope' and 'hate' are strictly speaking not antonyms, but nonetheless there is a clear sense of semantic opposition and used discursively this opposition can have ideological repercussions. This near-antonym represents of course the name of the activist group 'Hope not Hate' as well as radical activist campaigns such as 'Stop Funding Hate'. It is a convenient false polarising binary: you either subscribe to anti-racism and 'hope' or you are a 'hateful' fascist. 'Hate' is an example of Cassirer's (1946, p. 44) 'magic words' (with reference to fascism) by which he meant words whose meaning had changed and that were employed to create certain emotive effects. Language then no longer serves just a symbolic function. Where 'word magic' is concerned, there are no abstract denotations with 'every word being transformed into a mythical figure' (Cassirer, 1946, p. 97).⁹

Whilst 'hate' could not certainly be described as a harmonious discourse marker, 'hope' is. 'Hope' is also an example of a marker of solidarity because to oppose 'hate' and 'hate-speech' signals compassion. You are part of the struggle against 'hate' and are in solidarity with the pseudo-world of social justice which is synonymous with compassion. 'Hate' is ideological speak; a word that has been hi-jacked by social justice activists and taken to refer to anything that does not comply with their so-called 'values'—a series of semantically vacuous just-so statements that are trotted out by almost every single public and private institution in the Anglosphere that wishes to virtue-signal. 'Hate' can be attributed to any utterance that does not comply with the social justice ideology. Only the ethnic majority can be guilty of 'hate' and indeed this is now written into hate-speech legislation in most western European countries (Leonard, 2018).

'Hate speech' has often little to do with 'hate' in the true sense of the word. 'Hate-speech' could refer to simply stereotype enforcing statements or sometimes little more than rather innocent hyperbole. Rhetorically, the tactic here is to take a word or expression loaded with negative values and use it as a broad cover-term to refer to any opposing views as an attempt to normalise the social justice 'values'. A number of British universities now have Centres for Hate Studies. University of Leicester says its Centre for Hate Studies is committed 'to investigating hate crime'. Nottingham Trent University has a centre for study and reduction of hate crimes, bias and prejudice. According to the university, a 'hate crime' means a 'bias motivated behaviour'. Other universities such as the University of Massachusetts and Georgetown University keep 'daily crime logs' of 'bias incidents'. On their websites, they collocate 'bias' with 'hate' and imply they are synonymous, once again facilitating the idea that holding an opinion that goes against the social justice 'orthodoxy' is tantamount to a crime.

The word 'hate' typically means it is legally actionable and 'hate crime' along with 'hate speech' can only be considered such if the 'victim' can be perceived to hold some kind of minority group identity. Wolf-whistling is now a 'hate crime' in the UK. This is particularly perverse as men do it to show their appreciation for a woman. You could certainly call it 'sexist', but the reason it conveniently comes under the blanket term 'hate' is because women according to the feminist interpretation have historically been marginalised. Such an incident could only be considered a 'hate crime' if the meaning of 'hate' were re-engineered.

4.2. Harmonious 'values' (diversity, equity, inclusion, and belonging)

University websites in the Anglosphere speak incessantly of their 'values' and the importance of 'engaging' in them. These places of learning represent

ideological monocultures and echo-chambers for there is no option to critique or assess these collusion 'values'. The 'values' can only refer to one set of 'values': diversity, equity and inclusion—all of which come under the umbrella of 'social justice'. They can't be, say, 'stoicism', 'bravery' and 'critical awareness'. Like its discourse markers, these communitarian 'values' that appear throughout the social justice discourse are also meant to index compassion and harmony and therein lies the conspiracy. Indeed, the 'Offices of Inclusion and Belonging' at a number of US universities make this explicit such as Marquette University which runs 'Trans Compassion Weeks' comprising inter alia 'Gender affirming make-up workshops'.

The institutionalisation of social justice touches every aspect of the modern English-speaking university and where 'white privilege' is concerned university libraries are particularly affected. Janke (2011, p. 124) reminds us that 'social justice is a concern for librarians' and that it is the 'obligation of librarians to know their values and act on them'. The University of Madison talks about its campaign to disrupt whiteness and white supremacy in libraries. Cornell University says that historically libraries have upheld white supremacy. Many American university libraries such as Northern Illinois University bare a BIPOC (Black, Indigenous and People of Color) statement where they confess to having engaged in oppression and endeavour to dismantle systems of white supremacy. University websites in America are saturated with these kinds of statements. The tenet of every single university that appeared in the dataset was as follows: "Social justice is a core *value*, which runs through everything we do" (University of Newcastle).

The discourse of social justice is frequently just merged with that of 'inclusion' and 'diversity':

University La Verne/California runs courses on Social Justice; This course intersectionally explores *diversity* as an active, intentional, and ongoing *engagement* with intercultural differences and *power*—in people, the curriculum, the co-curricular, and in various communities and institutional types. Understanding the challenges of *diversity* and establishing/evaluating *diversity* and *inclusion* benchmarks in all spheres of the campus is essential to create a campus community where *diversity* and *inclusion* are centered throughout the institution. (University La Verne/California)

A great number of university websites in America and Canada talk about the objective of bias reporting as being to create an 'inclusive' community. As an example of 'inclusion', Syracuse university runs a LGBTQ resource centre where: "Trans, non-binary and gender conforming students can sample chest

binders before purchasing their own'. To ensure a 'safe environment based on inclusivity', trans students at the University of New Mexico can 'pick a room that aligns with their gender identity'. Many universities such as Roger Williams University speak of 'undoing heteronormativity' to bring about 'inclusion'.

Syracuse University hosts a large number of so-called affinity groups, for example, the Ace-Spec Affinity Groups for individuals that identify as asexual, aromantic, demi or gray and the QTPOC Affinity Group for queer and trans students of colour etc.; in the name of 'menstrual equity and inclusion', Brown University, University of Wisconsin-Madison, Emerson and many other campuses provide tampons for men. The Menstrual Dignity Act in Oregon means that local tax payers will have to pay for thousands of new tampon dispensers in men's bathrooms. The bill was justified using the language of safetyism: 'the state has decided to affirm the right to menstrual *dignity* for transgender, intersex, non-binary and two-spirit students who are at risk of *harm* during menstruation' (my italics) (Democratic Governor Kate Brown discussing in July 2021 The Menstrual Dignity Act, HB3294, 2021). Menstrual justice events are now common at British universities. What is more, in the spirit of 'inclusion', many universities in the US and the UK offer students 'trans roadmaps' helping them navigate the whole process of a sex change.

To support 'inclusion', many British universities have now made the GTRSB (Gypsies, Travellers, Roma, Showmen and Boaters) pledge where they support the 'inclusion' of students from these backgrounds in higher education.¹⁰ This is clearly an attempt to leverage off the perceived success of LGBTQ as an acronym. Acronyms reduce the complexity of thought by disassociating the nuanced or critical thought linked to words. 'Decolonisation' of curricula which is now very widely spread in the Anglosphere is normally marketed in terms of 'inclusion' (my italics):

Social justice and representation are woven through everything we do in the department. The notion of *decolonising* the curriculum has been happening here for many years, so we're always trying to be more *inclusive* and representative in our curricular content and in the modules that we teach. (Education Department, Goldsmiths, University of London) [italics mine]

Universities across the Anglosphere hold 'inclusive' 'Social Justice Related Events'. At NYU, recent events included: 'Building an *inclusive* and sustainable cannabis industry in New York State'; and 'Holding the Weight of Whiteness' (my italics). To further 'inclusion', many universities run 'ally networks'. The University of Chicago's Center for Identity + Inclusion states:

By displaying the *Safe Space* decal, allies are able to identify themselves as welcoming, *safe*, educated trained, and aware people, and pledge to promote a *safe* and affirming space for LGBTQ people by offering an atmosphere of respect, fairness, and trust. Allies will also be provided with programs and additional educational opportunities that will further their development as allies. (University of Chicago's Center for Identity + Inclusion) [italics mine]

More or less every ally network definition appears as: "The Ally Network aims to create a more diverse and inclusive culture at... by empowering..." "Acting as an ally for those that are experiencing a form of oppression is using the *power* of our unearned *privilege* to advocate and dismantle the systems that are ingrained into the foundation of American Privilege" (Drake University in the US states) [italics mine].

As examples of different types of privilege, it lists: Christian, heterosexual, right-handed, English speaking, whiteness etc. The kind of ideological thinking that these discourse markers aim to bring about shows an inability to be objective—the world is just seen as symbols of an ideology that intends to penetrate one's inner world. Every action of the opposition is judged by one moralising standard—every action of oneself by another. 'Inclusion' in fact means 'exclusion': as with many ideological terms, it has the opposite meaning. Similarly, 'diverse' means the opposite to what one might think it means: people who have no diversity of thought, people who unthinkingly and without any critical thinking subscribe to critical consciousness—the meme behind the social justice ideology. There are esoteric meanings and exoteric meanings (Moseley, 2011). This is the esoteric meaning—a 'diverse' person in the esoteric sense means a 'critical' theorist. It is not the exoteric meaning where 'diverse' might mean that lots of people held diverse political views. The social justice ideology prioritises esoteric meanings over exoteric meanings. It should be obvious that an 'inclusive' environment is one where a multitude of opinions are tolerated. Instead, 'inclusion' is defined as an environment where only the propaganda is welcomed. By endorsing only one take on identity politics, it creates the opposite—an 'exclusive' environment.

The use of such language aims to create a kind of systemic cognitive dissonance where people refuse to change their beliefs because of the perceived discomfort that it might bring about. Once an ideology can create cognitive dissonance at a systemic level, then it has begun to lay the course for an authoritarian mindset. Voloshinov (1973, p. 13) said that the 'individual consciousness is not the architect of the ideological superstructure, but only a tenant lodging in the edifice of ideological signs'. It is the crowd that determines the linguistic code but in line with Kierkegaard I would claim the

“crowd is untruth” (Kierkegaard, 1847, pp. 2,7). More recently, the word ‘belonging’ has become an ideological term—it means a cuddly welcoming sense of finding your place amidst a circle of like-minded, ‘virtuous’ people. But ‘belonging’ only extends to those who ‘engage with’ the social justice ideology. It is only once you ‘belong’ that you can become a social justice ‘champion’. The University of Berkeley has an Othering & Belonging Institute where they carry out ‘research’ on Belonging, Islamophobia, LGBTQ, Climate Justice, Global Justice, Narrative Power etc. The Institute ‘brings together researchers to develop strategic narratives for belonging’. They aim to ‘eliminate racialised inequality, create empathetic identities that bridge differences and promote an inclusive and responsive government’. These and many other similar institutes are ideological to the core. A great number of universities (Durham, Oxford, Stellenbosch, Westminster, Georgetown, Oklahoma, East London, Newcastle, Brighton, Leeds etc. just to name a few) have their own Centres for Social Justice.

The verb ‘to engage’ is used constantly throughout the social justice discourse. It is often employed to introduce one of the ideology’s slogans and is invariably collocated with one of the above harmonious discourse markers. According to the discourse, ‘engage’ means to embrace the social justice ideology. It is a clever rhetorical technique because in its non-ideological sense it means to be actively involved in something. It has a positive connotation. In the ideological sense, all that positivity is transferred to the social justice ‘cause’. ‘Engage’ and ‘empower’ are means of dealing with the alleged ‘victimhood’. The word ‘engage’ is used as a framing device: it couples a verb of action with positive associations related to ‘social justice’, and framing devices are used to shape the way we see the world. American University in Washington, DC has a whole page devoted to ‘Empowering Middle Schoolers to Seek Social Justice’ and the University of California talks about ‘empowering our next generation through social justice programmes’. Once students become ‘engaged’, they should aim to become equality, diversity, inclusion and social justice ‘champions’, i.e. ideological stalwarts.

In its GTRSB pledge, the Vice Chancellor of the University of Sussex says ‘we champion kindness, integrity, inclusion, collaboration and courage’. The university ‘seeks to build engagement’. She believes the GTRSB community ‘are subject to racism and hate crimes’. This pledge has subsequently been copied and pasted by a large number of British universities. All that matters is that you are ‘championing’ a cause related to social justice. The idea here is that you have ‘championed a cause’ and helped to tackle a discrimination in a society that is inherently racist.

5. Discussion

In this article, I have attempted to show how language creates social hierarchy and constitutes the new reality of social justice. Up to now, discourse analysis has been used largely to 'empower socially dominated groups' (Blommaert & Bulcaen, 2000; Huckin et al., 2012). Here, I have demonstrated how it can be used to unwrap the ideology that forces us to prioritise these alleged marginalised groups. Most of the Critical Discourse Analysis practitioners are embedded in the social justice ideology: the clue is the word 'critical'. CDA and social justice are therefore bed-fellows. It might seem strange therefore that I use this methodology to critique the social justice ideology, but critical research in the true sense of the word 'critical' should surely not just challenge unilaterally power relations in society. Using discourse analysis, I hope to have shown the hidden meanings in the social justice discourse and make it clear that the social justice ideology attempts to bring about its own power hierarchy.

It is generally recognised that relativism is important to discourse analysis. However, the relativists seem to have a worldview of their own, one that they exempt from their relativism to make their own pronouncements about no one belief being universally true. The social justice ideology would seem to assume that everybody of a certain ethnicity thinks exactly the same. The basis for the philosophy is the way somebody thinks is inextricably tied to their group identity. This is precisely the biological essentialism that the post-modernists are always complaining about. Total relativism undermines even the basic fundamentals of human society, and thus everything is up for reanalysis.

Discourse analysis can be taken to refer to the study of meanings people ascribe to language when it is used in a social context or at least that is one of the definitions. Many people who subscribe to the social justice ideology have no doubt honourable intentions and there are of course bona fide social injustices that should be addressed. However, discourse analysis shows that 'diversity' as used in the ideological sense does not mean diversity, 'inclusion' does not mean inclusion, 'values' can only refer to one set of values and 'safe spaces' have no connection with the notion of 'safety' in its non-ideological sense. 'Unprogressive' would appear to simply mean anything or anyone that does not comply with the diktats of the social justice ideology. The social justice ideology is in fact highly manipulative of language and achieves its objectives through the use of reiterative harmonious discourse markers. By appealing to universal and omnipresent marginalisation, the social justice ideologues seek to invert entirely alleged power relations. The objective might be understood to be revolution cloaked in empathy.

The social justice discourse has been bureaucratised and institutionalised to an extraordinary degree in the Anglosphere. My data analysis would seem to

suggest that this discourse has almost complete hegemony. If you wish to 'belong' you are encouraged to yield to the in-group's meaning of words. One of the purposes of the social justice ideology is to create a moral panic through 'othering' and the demonisation of alternative voices. As we have seen, othering is brought about through associating any alternative discourse with notions of 'danger' and 'hate' and through labelling.

6. Conclusion

This research showed that on the campuses of English-speaking universities there is no real alternative narrative to be found in the public space. The alternative narrative has to take place off-campus for reasons of censorship, self-censorship and widespread monitoring.

It would seem therefore that the social justice ideology is invested in its own fictions. In order to have any legitimacy, it perceives the need to perpetuate various injustices. Social justice and its appendage—the new moralism—is a code that generates connotative messages.¹¹ The objective is to make people completely dependent on the social justice definition of reality. This is what is happening in 'liberal democracies', not elsewhere in the world. The dynamics of herding have changed greatly since the time of Nietzsche, but he would no doubt agree that the social justice orthodoxy and its false moral fervour have been allowed to roam uncriticised for too long.

Notes

1. Nietzsche (*Ecce Homo*)'s notion of 'slave morality' implied that the man who is perceived to be 'good' would be him that sides with all those who are weak, sick and appear as a failure. He believed that the 'slaves' or the herd would lead a moral revolt and turn the 'masters' virtues' into vices.
2. As well as the Nietzschean notion of herd morality, one might invoke the concept of digital herding (Kushawa et al., 2022). Indeed, much of social media usage can be seen in terms of herd like behavior. Social media platforms have become a fertile ground for behavior convergence where digital connectivity is used to compete for followers and where echo chambers are created through filtering.
3. Micro-aggressions are defined as brief and commonplace daily verbal behavioral and environmental indignities, whether intentional or unintentional, that communicate hostile, derogatory or negative racial slights and insults that potentially have harmful or unpleasant psychological impact on the target person or group (Solorzano et al., 2000).

4. I agree with Hayek (1976) that the term has come to mean too many things. This semantic imprecision is convenient for ideologues though as it gives the movement a charitable veneer ('justice') and means that it can pursue its propaganda through a number of related channels at the same time.
5. With virtue-signalling in mind, one is reminded of the passage in the book of Matthew: "Be careful not to practice your righteousness in front of others to be seen by them. If you do, you will have no reward from your Father in heaven" [6:1].
6. One might note that the rainbow is in Christianity associated with God's protection; pride is one of the deadly sins; the seven sins, and the seven colours of the rainbow, etc.
7. The University of Queensland makes white students sit white privilege tests. These tests are used in the UK too (University of Kent and University of Cambridge). At George Brown College in Toronto, white students have to sign a waiver saying how they benefited from 'the colonization and genocide of indigenous peoples'.
8. Cf. "One small step for man, one giant step for mankind." (Neil Armstrong)
9. Cassirer (1946) believed that the prerequisite for mythical thinking was the focus on specific words whose meaning had been made emotive.
10. One would have assumed the word 'Gypsy' was derogatory.
11. For more on morals and ethics, see Kamm (2007) and Salmani Nodoushan (2015, 2016, 2019, 2021a).

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